

Comparative Evaluation of Sustainable Bio-Oils and Conventional Diesel in Invert Emulsion Muds

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Article History:

Received: 21.02.2026 Revised: 06.03.2026 Accepted: 09.03.2026 Published: 10.03.2026

ABSTRACT:

The global transition toward sustainable drilling practices has intensified the search for biodegradable alternatives to mitigate the environmental risks associated with conventional diesel-based drilling fluids. This study reports a comparative investigation on the use of Castor Seed Oil (CSO) and Palm Kernel Oil (PKO) as environmentally friendly continuous phases in invert emulsion muds. Four different systems were analyzed including a standard diesel oil (Sample A), single source bio-oils (Samples B and C) and a PKO/CSO bio-blend (Sample D). Bio-oils were extracted using the Soxhlet extraction and were formulated as 350 mL laboratory barrel mud systems. Results showed the PKO/CSO bio-blend (Sample D) is an optimized and technically superior alternative to commercial diesel. Physicochemical analysis showed that, although the diesel-based mud had slightly acidic pH values of 6.5, the pH composition of bio-based formulations was neutral with pH equal to 7.0, indicating improved chemical stability, as well as lower corrosion potential. In addition, Sample D produced a good enough density of 8.31 PPG, which can guarantee the proper hydrostatic pressure for normal drilling operations. Rheological testing proved to be a significant synergistic effect in the binary blending of PKO and CSO. Sample D reached a Yield Point (YP) of 52 lb/100ft², representing a 48.6% increase over the diesel control (35 lb/100ft²). This led to an Apparent Viscosity (AV) of 71 cP which is almost 2.5 times more viscous than control (29 cP) confirming a stronger emulsion for optimum cuttings transportability. The bio-blend also optimized the Plastic Viscosity (PV) to 33 cP to offer efficient YP/PV ratio of 1.57 and a gel-strength of 4lb/100ft², which ensures reliable cuttings suspension while minimizing breakdown pressures during pump startup. Rheological measurements confirmed that all formulations exhibit pseudoplastic (shear-thinning) behavior. Sample D showed the highest shear stress across all shear rates, indicating the highest structural integrity and dynamic cutting carrying capacity as compared to the other mud samples tested. This study concludes that the PKO/CSO blend effectively bridges the gap between sustainable base oil technology and high performance drilling requirements, offering eco-friendly alternative to conventional drilling base oils.

Keywords: Invert Emulsion Mud, Sustainable Drilling Fluids, Castor Seed Oil, Palm Kernel Oil, Bio-oil Blends, Rheological Synergies.

Suggested Citation: E.A. Temple, M.L. Kpea-ue, "Comparative Evaluation of Sustainable Bio-Oils and Conventional Diesel in Invert Emulsion Muds," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 4(2), pp. 130-137, Mar-Apr 2026. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2026.4(2).07

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INTRODUCTION

Oil and gas industry is one of the largest and key industries in the world, both in terms of strategy and economy. Oil and gas production require drilling into the ground, and this is likely to cause pollution. In the oil and gas exploration, drilling fluids are critical, and they have been demonstrated to make the process more successful through their ability to stabilize the wellbore, carry off the cuttings, and manage the pressure. Selecting a competent drilling fluid for a successful drilling operation strongly depends on the cost of formulating the mud, mud technical performance and the environmental impact of the mud [5, 7]. Drilling fluid, or drilling mud, is defined as any fluid that circulates inside the well passing through the drill string and returning to the surface through the annular space. The industry today is facing two forces: the need to have high-performance fluids in deepwater and horizontal wells, and the worldwide requirement to have a net-zero emissions and sustainable industry. Conventionally, drilling fluids which are normally made up of water, synthetic oil or diesel provide exceptional lubricity and wellbore stability when over against water based counterparts. The vast majority of traditional drilling fluids additives are mainly composed of fossil-based, non-renewable substances hence, adding to the drilling operations a great contribution to the environmental pollution and to the growing and more demanding environmental regulations.

Oil-based mud is a fluid in which the continuous phase is oil-based fluid [1]. It composes of liquid hydrocarbons and most common fluid is diesel. It was first introduced to address drilling problems particularly in high-pressure, high temperature (HPHT) environments. [11,14]. However, the environmental impact of conventional diesel-based fluids has raised concerns regarding their sustainability and potential harm to ecosystems. To address these challenges, recent research has pivoted toward bio-based oils [6,9,12,13,16] derived from non-edible plant feedstocks and vegetable oils oil is recognized for its oxidative stability, provides exceptional lubricity and low-temperature flow properties.

Plant oil is a liquid emulsion of oxygenated organic compounds, polymers, and water. It is a liquid product produced by pyrolysis: rapid heating and rapid quenching of organic material of biomass, in a low oxygen atmosphere. Because of the unique properties of liquefied biomass, it is more easily pumped, stored and more compatible to chemical modification, processing or extraction. Different studies have evaluated bio-oil successfully for drilling. Studies on castor oil, palm oil, soya bean oil, jatropha oil, canola oil, algae oil, moringa seed oil and soap-nut have shown to be significant as a plant oil source for diesel substitute production [15]. Most existing studies focus either on water-based mud additives or single-source bio-oils. This study addresses this research gap by formulating an invert emulsion mud that leverages the high-viscosity characteristics of locally sourced bio-oils.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and Apparatus

The primary raw materials, Castor seeds and Palm kernels, were procured from the Mile 3 Market in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Commercial-grade Diesel was utilized as the control continuous phase. The chemical additives employed for mud formulation included Potassium Chloride (KCl), Borax, Xanthan Gum, Polyanionic Cellulose (PAC), Barite, Soda Ash, Caustic Soda, and Bentonite. The experimental procedures were facilitated using a Soxhlet extractor, a heating mantle, a high-speed electric mixer, an 8-speed rotational viscometer, a mud balance, and pH indicator strips.

Sample Preparation and Oil Extraction

The seeds and kernels were manually cleaned and crushed to optimize surface area for extraction. The bio-oils were extracted via the Soxhlet method using toluene as the solvent. A 50g of the crushed sample was refluxed at 70°C for a 24-hour duration. After the extraction cycles, the oil-solvent mixture was simple distilled to separate the mixture at 70°C. The toluene recovered was stored to be reused again and the Castor Seed Oil (CSO) and the Palm Kernel Oil (PKO) were left to be reused in glass reagent bottles to be used in formulation later.

Formulation of Drilling Mud Samples

Three mud systems were formulated based on a 350 mL laboratory barrel. The standardized composition for each system is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Mud Formulation and Additive Concentration

S/N	Material	Quantity
1	Base Fluid (Diesel/CSO/PKO)	350 mL
2	Water	350 mL
3	Potassium Chloride	18.0 g
4	Barite	76.80 g
5	Xanthan Gum / Bentonite	2.80 g each
6	PAC / Borax	2.00 g each
7	Soda Ash / Caustic Soda	0.20 g each

It was formulated by adding 76.8g of barite to the base fluid in 10 minutes. The mixture obtained was left to mature over a period of 24 hours in order to offer due yielding. Then, the rest of the additives were added after every 3 minutes with constant high-shear mixing until a uniform invert emulsion was obtained.

Analytical Procedures

Rheological Measurements

The rheological profile was measured using an eight-speed rotational viscometer. Dial readings were taken with 600, 300, 200, 100, 60, 30 and 6 rpm. These were used in calculating the apparent viscosity (AV), plastic viscosity (PV) and the yield point (YP) using the Bingham plastic model. Measurement of gel strength was done at the points of time of 10 seconds and 10 minutes. The maximum deflection was measured at 3 rpm under stationary conditions.

Physical Property Testing

A standard mud balance was used in the determination of the mud density. The sample was put in the cup which was then poised on the knife-edge to measure the weight. The pH of the systems was measured by immersing pH strips in the samples and allowed 10 minutes to pass and comparing the caused color change with a calibrated chart.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Density and Pressure of Mud Systems

The density and resulting hydrostatic pressure gradients for the four formulated mud systems are illustrated in Figure 1. Pure diesel mud (Sample 0) had a specific gravity of 8.70ppt with a hydrostatic pressure gradient value of 441 psi/1000 ft. Conversely, the single-source bio- oils, Sample B (PKO) and Sample C (CSO) had lower densities of 8.20 0 PPG and 8.31 0 PPG respectively. This means that the PKO/CSO bio-blend (Sample D) has enough levels of hydrostatic pressure to conduct normal drilling operations and can be used as a viable alternative to continuous phases using diesel.

pH Analysis

pH of a drilling fluid is one of the basic parameters that determine the stability of the emulsion, the effectiveness of chemical additives, and the prevention of downhole corrosion. All the formulated systems of mud have a range of pH values ranging within the slightly acidic and slightly neutral values (6.5 to 7.0) as showed in Figure (2). The lowest pH was also observed in the diesel (Sample A) of 6.5. Contrarily, the available bio-based formulations - Sample B (PKO), Sample C (CSO) and the Bio-blend (Sample D) all had a neutral pH of 7.0. This means that the bio-base oils (PKO and CSO) have more reliable and less acidic chemical composition than the commercial diesel.

Figure 1. Comparative Density and Pressure Gradient of Formulated Mud

Figure 2. Comparative pH Profile of Mud Formulations

The Rheological Properties of the Formulated Muds

Plastic Viscosity

Figure 3 shows the drilling fluids viscosity of plastics (PV). Sample A was the least PV 17 cP of commercial diesel-based mud. Sample do bio-oils, Sample B (palm oil, PKO) and Sample C (castor oil, CSO) had greater internal resistance, having PV 41cP and 48cP respectively. Conversely, the PKO/CSO confound (SampleD) showed a very significant moderating effect with the PV decreasing by 33cP. This decrease indicates that the binary mixing of PKO and CSO promotes interactions between the molecules, hence a more flowable continuous phase, which reduces frictional pressure loss during the circulatory process.

Yield Point

One of the very important indicators of the dynamism-carrying capacity of the fluid is the yield point (YP). One of the main results of the research is that the PKO/CSO blend (Sample D), which achieved a YP of 52lb/100ft², a 48.6% increase over the diesel benchmark (35lb/100ft²), despite a slight decrease in the density of the bio-blend, the significantly higher YP gives the bio-blend a technical edge in cleaning holes and cuttings suspension.

Apparent Viscosity (AV)

Apparent viscosity (AV) is the total fluid impediment to flow of the drilling fluid including mechanical friction (plastic viscosity) as well as electrochemical forces (yield point). From Figure 3, the AV values of the bio-based formulations were dramatically high as compared to the diesel oil. This significant rise shows that the palm kernel oil/ castor oil synergistic interaction forms a stronger and firmer emulsion.

Synergistic Effect

In Figure 3, Sample D achieved an optimized YP/PV ratio of 1.57, which is lower than the 2.06 observed in Sample A, which indicates a more efficient rheological balance. While Sample A exhibits excessively high structured viscosity that could lead to high circulating pressures, the PKO/CSO blend (Sample D) creates a more robust yet pumpable emulsion. This allows for better cuttings transport without the hydraulic risks associated with the higher ratio found in Sample A. The Apparent Viscosity (AV) of the formulations further supports the high performance of the bio-blend. Sample D achieved an AV of 71 cP, a significant indicator of the fluid's total resistance to flow.

Figure 3. Comparative Rheological Profile of Commercial Diesel Versus Bio-Diesel

Gel strength

As it is evident in Figure 4, PKO/CSO blend (Sample D) exhibits a highly desirable gel characteristic. While the 10-second gel strength of Sample D (4lb/100ft²) is numerically lower than the control (Sample A), which recorded a value of 7lb/100ft², this reduction represents a significant advantage in hydraulic management when contrasted with its Yield Point (52lb/100ft²). The lower initial gel strength (10secs) of the bio-blend indicates a fluid that maintains good dynamic carrying capacity during circulation. However, once circulation ceases, Sample D develops a low-resistance internal structure that is more easily broken upon the resumption of pumping compared to sample A. Consequently, this trend ensures that the PKO/CSO formulation provides reliable cuttings suspension while minimizing the breakdown pressures required to restart circulation, thereby reducing the risk of induced formation fractures and pressure spikes often associated with the diesel oil.

Shear stress and Shear Rate

The relationship between shear stress and shear rate as illustrated in (Figure 5), provides a comprehensive view of the flow behavior of the formulated mud systems. All samples, including the diesel (Sample A) and the bio-based formulations (Samples B, C, and D), exhibit non-Newtonian, shear-thinning (pseudoplastic) behavior. PKO/CSO blend (Sample D) shows the highest shear stress across the entire range of shear rates, particularly at higher speeds. This upward shift in the rheological curve confirms the synergistic effect of blending PKO and CSO, resulting in a more robust fluid structure.

Figure 4. Comparative Analysis of 10-sec Gel-Strength

Figure 5. Rheological Flow Curves Showing the Relationship between Shear Stress and Shear Rate

CONCLUSION

This study presented a comparative evaluation of sustainable bio-oils against a conventional diesel oil for the formulation of invert emulsion muds. The important findings are as follows:

- Physicochemical Stability:** While the diesel oil (Sample A) exhibited a slightly acidic pH of 6.5, the bio-based formulations (Samples B, C, and D) maintained a neutral pH of 7.0, suggesting enhanced chemical stability and reduced corrosion potential. Furthermore, Sample D provided a sufficient density of 8.31 PPG, ensuring adequate hydrostatic pressure for standard drilling operations.
- Synergistic Rheological Performance:** A significant synergistic effect was observed in the binary blending of PKO and CSO. Sample D achieved a Yield Point (YP) of 52lb/100ft² a 48.6% increase over the diesel (35lb/100ft²). This resulted in a total Apparent Viscosity (AV) of 71cP, nearly 2.5 times higher than the control (29cP), confirming a more robust and structured emulsion for an optimum cuttings transport
- Optimized Flow:** The bio-blend optimized the Plastic Viscosity (PV) to 33cP, resulting in an efficient YP/PV ratio of 1.57. This balance, combined with a 10-second gel strength (4lb/100ft²),

ensures reliable cuttings suspension during circulation while minimizing breakdown pressures during pump start-up.

- **Non-Newtonian Characteristics:** Rheological measurements confirmed that all formulations exhibit pseudoplastic (shear-thinning) behavior. Sample D showed the highest shear stress across all shear rates, indicating the highest structural integrity and dynamic cutting carrying capacity as compared to the other mud samples tested.

Summarily, the PKO/CSO blend (Sample D) effectively bridges the gap between sustainable base-oil technology and high-performance drilling requirements. Its unique combination of high dynamic capacity and gel behavior makes it a highly viable, eco-friendly substitute for commercial diesel in modern drilling environments.

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